

Explanatory Sheet to Obtain Research Parent's/Guidance's Subject Approval

MOODMIND: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR MAJOR DEPRESSIVE DISORDER SCREENING IN TUBERCULOSIS PATIENTS

Good morning/afternoon/ Mr./Ms/Mrs

I am ERLINA WIJAYANTI, a researcher at YARSI University. I am currently conducting a research entitled Moodmind: Artificial Intelligence For Major Depressive Disorder Screening In Tuberculosis Patients.

This study aims to measure the accuracy of the AI MOOD MIND tool to detect depression. In this study we will:

- Ask respondents to use the AI MOOD MIND product through conversation
- Conducting interviews/anamnesis with patients via video call/zoom

I would like to ask your permission as a parent/guardian. Once you know the information about this activity and you agree, I will ask for your Child's willingness. Activities can be done after you and your child agree to the activity plan that I conveyed.

Before you make a decision, you can ask or discuss this activity with anyone you feel comfortable with. If you want to ask, I'll help explain it to you.

If you agree, please select the answer "Yes". If you don't agree, select "No."

Yes

No

Thus we convey this explanation. Thank you for your attention and willingness of time.

Researchers

Erlina Wijayanti

INFORMATION

Research Title: MOODMIND: Artificial Intelligence for Major Depressive Disorder Screening in Tuberculosis Patients

The information provided is as follows:

TYPES OF INFORMATION	CONTENTS INFORMATION
Research Objectives	Measuring the accuracy of the AI MOOD MIND tool to detect Major Depressive Disorder
Research Time	For 3 months (May-July 2025)
Method	In this study, it will involve cadres, researchers, and doctors for data collection. Patients fill out an approval questionnaire and then be contacted for an interview.
Data collection procedure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients will be called via video call/zoom meeting. Patients can be accompanied by family • The patient will be explained about the research protocol • Patients will be sent an AI link and explained how to use it by the researcher • Patients use AI by responding verbally to questions posed by AI • AI will provide conclusions (category Depression/ risk/ no) • The patient shows the results of these conclusions to the researcher and the researcher documents them • Next, the patient will be anamnesis by a doctor to detect MDD • The doctor will diagnose whether the patient is classified as MDD or not
Advantages and Benefits for research subjects	The study allowed patients to know the symptoms of depression early
Loss	There is no potential harm in this study, except that TB patients need to take the time to participate in the study
Data collection procedure	TB patients fill in the willingness through gform, then will be called by the researcher and data collection is carried out via vieo call/zoom
Alternative Procedures	There are no other procedural alternatives

Possible discomfort	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. TB patients need to answer questions from AI or doctors2. Patients need to have an internet network
Rewards to be given	TB patients will get a credit of IDR 40,000 after the research
Respondent's Rights	Respondents or samples have the right to ask questions and objections to participate